

Paired T-Test Report

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber1_U_neo, X2 = odber2_U_neox

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_neo	65	247,3385	73,51834	9,118828	229,1215	265,5554
odber2_U_neox	65	281,2308	81,95193	10,16489	260,9241	301,5375
Difference	65	-33,89231	82,68958	10,25638	-54,38178	-13,40283

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9977

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	1,5429	0,122863	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	2,4392	0,014720	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality	8,3302	0,015528	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,438467		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_neo-odber2_U_neox<>0		-3,3045	0,001561	Yes	0,902265
odber1_U_neo-odber2_U_neox<0		-3,3045	0,000781	Yes	0,947856
odber1_U_neo-odber2_U_neox>0		-3,3045	0,999219	No	0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	44	21	0,005918	0,002959	0,998687

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
555	1072,5	153,018	0	8	84

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			3,3820	0,000000	Yes	3,3787	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-3,3820	0,000360	Yes	-3,3787	0,000364	Yes
X1-X2>0			-3,3820	0,999640	No	-3,3852	0,999644	No

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Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_neo, X2 = odber3_U_neox

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_neo	62	253,0323	80,77412	10,25832	232,5195	273,545
odber3_U_neox	62	353,1129	84,27494	10,70293	331,7111	374,5147
Difference	62	-100,0806	118,253	15,01815	-130,1113	-70,05

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9996

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	0,2337	0,815214	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	1,5018	0,133146	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	2,3101	0,315049	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	-0,026226		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_neo-odber3_U_neox<>0	-6,6640	0,000000	Yes	0,999998	0,999952
odber1_U_neo-odber3_U_neox<0	-6,6640	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	0,999986

odber1_U_neo-odber3_U_neox>0 -6,6640 1,000000 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	53	9	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
244	976,5	142,6249	0	9	90

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			5,1358	0,000000	Yes	5,1323	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-5,1358	0,000000	Yes	-5,1323	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2>0			-5,1358	1,000000	No	-5,1394	1,000000	No

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 Variable X1 = odber2_U_neox, X2 = odber3_U_neox

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber2_U_neox	59	281,2542	82,31763	10,71684	259,8022	302,7063
odber3_U_neox	59	349,8813	84,91133	11,05451	327,7534	372,0094
Difference	59	-68,62712	111,1386	14,46901	-97,59	-39,66424

T for Confidence Limits = 2,0017

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	2,2525	0,024289	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	2,8252	0,004725	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality	13,0557	0,001462	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,116910		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber2_U_neox-odber3_U_neox<>0	-4,7430	0,000014	Yes	0,996567	0,978804
odber2_U_neox-odber3_U_neox<0	-4,7430	0,000007	Yes	0,998825	0,989398

odber2_U_neox-odber3_U_neox>0 -4,7430 0,999993 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	49	10	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
255,5	885	132,4802	0	9	72

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			4,7517	0,000002	Yes	4,7479	0,000002	Yes
X1-X2<0			-4,7517	0,000001	Yes	-4,7479	0,000001	Yes
X1-X2>0			-4,7517	0,999999	No	-4,7554	0,999999	No

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 Variable X1 = odber2_U_neox, X2 = odber3_U_neox

Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn, X2 = odber2_U_kynx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_kyn	63	0,6736508	0,3563674	4,489808E-02	0,5839008	0,7634008
odber2_U_kynx	63	0,9061905	0,4812196	6,062798E-02	0,7849969	1,027384
Difference	63	-0,2325397	0,3793457	4,779306E-02	-0,3280767	-0,1370027

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9990

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-1,7967	0,072391	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	1,9410	0,052264	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	6,9953	0,030269	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,625884		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_kyn-odber2_U_kynx<>0	-4,8656	0,000008	Yes	0,997665	0,984525
odber1_U_kyn-odber2_U_kynx<0	-4,8656	0,000004	Yes	0,999229	0,992480

odber1_U_kyn-odber2_U_kynx>0 -4,8656 0,999996 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	46	17	0,000337	0,000168	0,999941

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
360,5	1008	146,0574	0	11	156

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			4,4332	0,000009	Yes	4,4298	0,000009	Yes
X1-X2<0			-4,4332	0,000005	Yes	-4,4298	0,000005	Yes
X1-X2>0			-4,4332	0,999995	No	-4,4366	0,999995	No

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn, X2 = odber2_U_kynx

Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn, X2 = odber3_U_kynx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_kyn	62	0,6870968	0,3588889	4,557894E-02	0,595956	0,7782375
odber3_U_kynx	62	1,365	0,644741	8,188219E-02	1,201266	1,528734
Difference	62	-0,6779032	0,5323968	6,761446E-02	-0,8131067	-0,5426998

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9996

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-2,1589	0,030855	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	1,0835	0,278603	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	5,8349	0,054071	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,564081		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_kyn-odber3_U_kynx<>0	-10,0260	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
odber1_U_kyn-odber3_U_kynx<0	-10,0260	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000

odber1_U_kyn-odber3_U_kynx>0 -10,0260 1,000000 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	58	4	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
43	976,5	142,6267	0	8	66

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			6,5451	0,000000	Yes	6,5416	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-6,5451	0,000000	Yes	-6,5416	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2>0			-6,5451	1,000000	No	-6,5486	1,000000	No

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn, X2 = odber3_U_kynx

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 Variable X1 = odber2_U_kynx, X2 = odber3_U_kynx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber2_U_kynx	57	0,9384211	0,4889486	6,476282E-02	0,8086855	1,068157
odber3_U_kynx	57	1,390877	0,6532372	8,652338E-02	1,21755	1,564204
Difference	57	-0,4524561	0,4590957	6,080871E-02	-0,5742706	-0,3306417

T for Confidence Limits = 2,0032

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-2,2321	0,025608	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	0,9629	0,335594	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	5,9095	0,052091	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,712307		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber2_U_kynx-odber3_U_kynx<>0	-7,4406	0,000000	0,000000	Yes	1,000000
odber2_U_kynx-odber3_U_kynx<0	-7,4406	0,000000	0,000000	Yes	1,000000

odber2_U_kynx-odber3_U_kynx>0 -7,4406 1,000000 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	47	9	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
106	826	125,8546	1	10	78

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			5,7209	0,000000	Yes	5,7169	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-5,7209	0,000000	Yes	-5,7169	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2>0			-5,7209	1,000000	No	-5,7249	1,000000	No

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 Variable X1 = odber2_U_kynx, X2 = odber3_U_kynx

Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_trp, X2 = odber2_U_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_trp	65	11,858	4,116266	0,5105599	10,83804	12,87796
odber2_U_trpx	65	13,29631	4,69614	0,5824845	12,13266	14,45995
Difference	65	-1,438308	3,507539	0,4350567	-2,307433	-0,5691821

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9977

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-2,1154	0,034392	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	0,6091	0,542444	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	4,8461	0,088650	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,690475		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_trp-odber2_U_trpx<>0	-3,3060	0,001554	Yes	0,902522	0,740275
odber1_U_trp-odber2_U_trpx<0	-3,3060	0,000777	Yes	0,948016	0,818427

odber1_U_trp-odber2_U_trpx>0 -3,3060 0,999223 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	44	21	0,005918	0,002959	0,998687

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
639	1072,5	153,0217	0	5	30

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			2,8329	0,004612	Yes	2,8297	0,004660	Yes
X1-X2<0			-2,8329	0,002306	Yes	-2,8297	0,002330	Yes
X1-X2>0			-2,8329	0,997694	No	-2,8362	0,997717	No

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_trpx, X2 = odber2_U_trpx

Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_trpx	62	12,1429	3,984735	0,5060619	11,13097	13,15484
odber3_U_trpx	62	16,71952	5,537613	0,7032775	15,31323	18,12581
Difference	62	-4,576613	4,254164	0,5402793	-5,656968	-3,496258

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9996

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-1,9784	0,047879	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	0,5785	0,562911	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	4,2489	0,119497	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,644554		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<>0	-8,4708	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
odber1_U_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<0	-8,4708	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000

odber1_U_trp-odber3_U_trpx>0 -8,4708 1,000000 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	53	9	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
92	976,5	142,6306	0	2	12

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			6,2013	0,000000	Yes	6,1978	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-6,2013	0,000000	Yes	-6,1978	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2>0			-6,2013	1,000000	No	-6,2048	1,000000	No

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Plots Section

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 Variable X1 = odber2_U_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber2_U_trpx	59	13,59288	4,78704	0,6232195	12,34537	14,84039
odber3_U_trpx	59	16,84085	5,603664	0,7295349	15,38052	18,30117
Difference	59	-3,247966	3,828029	0,498367	-4,245556	-2,250376

T for Confidence Limits = 2,0017

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	1,3305	0,183356	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	0,6306	0,528321	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	2,1678	0,338269	Cannot reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,739293		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber2_U_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<>0	-6,5172	0,000000	Yes	0,999996	0,999912
odber2_U_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<0	-6,5172	0,000000	Yes	0,999999	0,999973

odber2_U_trpx-odber3_U_trpx>0 -6,5172 1,000000 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	50	9	0,000000	0,000000	1,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
205	885	132,4844	0	3	18

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			5,1327	0,000000	Yes	5,1289	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			-5,1327	0,000000	Yes	-5,1289	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2>0			-5,1327	1,000000	No	-5,1365	1,000000	No

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber2_U_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Plots Section

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn_trpx, X2 = odber2_U_kyn_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_kyn_trp	63	55,96254	22,79599	2,872025	50,22144	61,70364
odber2_U_kyn_trpx	63	68,11047	29,30556	3,692153	60,72997	75,49098
Difference	63	-12,14794	26,20804	3,301903	-18,74835	-5,547526

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9990

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	-0,5691	0,569282	Cannot reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	2,5363	0,011204	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality	6,7566	0,034106	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	0,517635		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)	
odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber2_U_kyn_trpx<>0	-3,6791	0,000492	Yes	0,951698	0,842358	
odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber2_U_kyn_trpx<0	-3,6791	0,000246	Yes	0,976904	0,898275	

odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber2_U_kyn_trpx>0 -3,6791 0,999754 No 0,000000 0,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	44	19	0,002228	0,001114	0,999551

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
460	1008	146,0685	0	0	0

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			3,7517	0,000176	Yes	3,7482	0,000178	Yes
X1-X2<0			-3,7517	0,000088	Yes	-3,7482	0,000089	Yes
X1-X2>0			-3,7517	0,999912	No	-3,7551	0,999913	No

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn_trp, X2 = odber2_U_kyn_trpx

Plots Section

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn_trp, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber1_U_kyn_trp	62	57,17871	25,29052	3,2119	50,75612	63,6013
odber3_U_trpx	62	16,71952	5,537613	0,7032775	15,31323	18,12581
Difference	62	40,45919	26,23694	3,332095	33,79626	47,12213

T for Confidence Limits = 1,9996

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(,050)
Skewness Normality	3,8889	0,000101	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	2,6756	0,007458	Reject normality
Omnibus Normality	22,2828	0,000014	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	-0,064625		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber3_U_trpx<>0	12,1423	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber3_U_trpx<0	12,1423	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

odber1_U_kyn_trp-odber3_U_trpx>0 12,1423 0,000000 Yes 1,000000 1,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	1	61	0,000000	1,000000	0,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
1951	976,5	142,6311	0	1	6

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			6,8323	0,000000	Yes	6,8288	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			6,8323	1,000000	No	6,8358	1,000000	No
X1-X2>0			6,8323	0,000000	Yes	6,8288	0,000000	Yes

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 Variable X1 = odber1_U_kyn_trp, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Plots Section

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 Database S:\Vyzkum\Chromed\Statistika\personmed\moč Farag.S0
 Variable X1 = odber2_U_kyn_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Descriptive Statistics Section

Variable	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	95,0% LCL of Mean	95,0% UCL of Mean
odber2_U_kyn_trpx	57	69,07649	29,43334	3,898541	61,26677	76,88621
odber3_U_trpx	57	17,09807	5,500349	0,728539	15,63863	18,55751
Difference	57	51,97842	29,98149	3,971146	44,02326	59,93358

T for Confidence Limits = 2,0032

Tests of Assumptions about Differences Section

Assumption	Value	Probability	Decision(.050)
Skewness Normality	2,9376	0,003307	Reject normality
Kurtosis Normality	1,4773	0,139586	Cannot reject normality
Omnibus Normality	10,8121	0,004489	Reject normality
Correlation Coefficient	-0,007149		

T-Test For Difference Between Means Section

Alternative Hypothesis	T-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Power (Alpha=.05)	Power (Alpha=.01)
odber2_U_kyn_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<>0	13,0890	0,000000	Yes	1,000000	1,000000
odber2_U_kyn_trpx-odber3_U_trpx<0	13,0890	1,000000	No	0,000000	0,000000

odber2_U_kyn_trpx-odber3_U_trpx>0 13,0890 0,000000 Yes 1,000000 1,000000

Nonparametric Tests Section

Quantile (Sign) Test

Null Quantile (Q0)	Quantile Proportion	Number Lower	Number Higher	H1:Q<>Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q<Q0 Prob Level	H1:Q>Q0 Prob Level
0	0,5	1	56	0,000000	1,000000	0,000000

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for Difference in Medians

W Sum Ranks	Mean of W	Std Dev of W	Number of Zeros	Number Sets of Ties	Multiplicity Factor
1652	826,5	125,862	0	0	0

Alternative Hypothesis	Exact Probability		Approximation Without Continuity Correction			Approximation With Continuity Correction		
	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050	Z-Value	Prob Level	Reject H0 at ,050
X1-X2<>0			6,5588	0,000000	Yes	6,5548	0,000000	Yes
X1-X2<0			6,5588	1,000000	No	6,5627	1,000000	No
X1-X2>0			6,5588	0,000000	Yes	6,5548	0,000000	Yes

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Variable X1 = odber2_U_kyn_trpx, X2 = odber3_U_trpx

Plots Section

